

From Chernobyl to Florida across Garigliano. Analysis of chemical disasters

Vinci A. ¹, Marchetti M. ², Monti M. ², Zelinotti L. ³, Rosiello F. ¹

1 Sapienza University of Rome, 2 USL Umbria 1, 3 Istituto Zooprofilattico Lazio

BACKGROUND:

215 million gallons of water contaminated by radio-waste of phosphoric fertilizer (called "gypsum stack" or "phosphogypsum") probably spilled into biggest Florida's aquifer on August 2016, 27th, but Mosaic society advised Authority only on September, 17th. In the last 20 years, this was the third incident for Mosaic.

Uranium and thorium, and likely cadmium too, are the responsible of radioactive pollution in this case, due to their presence in Phosphogypsum, a waste generated by the phosphoric fertilizer.

METHODS

Scientific publications in the last 30 years and current evidences were collected.

In the first part of review we analyzed history of nuclear Centrale del Garigliano (Italy). In the second part, a meta-analysis regarding Chernobyl incident has been performed, focused on the use of contaminated water. We use data only by Centrale del Garigliano and Chernobyl (and not other, such Fukushima) because in study we considered only spilling in not current water, that is used for agriculture and livestock. To study Floridian pollution, we compare Italian radioactivity/wide from nuclear/population density (and its effects on public health) with Floridian data, and we add to this cadmium toxicity.

(from left: Centrale del Garigliano, Mosaic logo, Chernobyl nuclear skeleton)

FINDINGS:

Florida is known for sinkholes, but Florida is known also for fertilizer production: is possible combine natural and artificial hazards with people health safety and national security? Review analyzes agricultural/human use of undeclared contaminated water in the past (Chernobyl), and currently (Centrale del Garigliano) to predict which hazards for public health are more likely to occur in Florida.

TEST: RESULT
 map demonstrates Nitrum increasing ($\Delta^{15}\text{N}$) into Gaeta Gulf (kringing mode).
 On the axis are GPS coordinates.
 Red: higher organic concentrations, yellow: high ones, light blue: higher inorganic concentrations.

CONCLUSIONS

Use of contaminated water is strictly correlated with increase of cardio-vascular disease, miscarriages/infant malformations and cancer due to DNA pathologies (duplications, deletions, etc).
 It is auspicious a more synergic effort between private and/or public agencies, for adequate prevention and better management of similar accidents in the future.

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